

1 **DelSIEVE: cell phylogeny modeling of single nucleotide variants**
2 **and deletions from single-cell DNA sequencing data**

3 **Supplementary tables**

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Table S1: Definition of the distribution of the number of sequenced alleles (α_{ij}) conditional on the true genotype (g_{ij}) and on the allelic ADO rate (θ_A) under the ADO mode for DelSIEVE.

α_{ij}	g_{ij}	ADO occurred	$P(\alpha_{ij} g_{ij}, \theta_A)$
1	0/0	Yes	θ_A
2	0/0	No	$1 - \theta_A$
1	0/1	Yes	θ_A
2	0/1	No	$1 - \theta_A$
1	1/1	Yes	θ_A
2	1/1	No	$1 - \theta_A$
1	1/1'	Yes	θ_A
2	1/1'	No	$1 - \theta_A$
0	0/-	Yes	$\theta_A/2$
1	0/-	No	$1 - \theta_A/2$
0	1/-	Yes	$\theta_A/2$
1	1/-	No	$1 - \theta_A/2$
0	-	No	1
Others			0

Table S2: Definition of the distribution of α_{ij} conditional on g_{ij} and θ_L under LDO mode for DelSIEVE. Definition of the distribution of the number of sequenced alleles (α_{ij}) conditional on the true genotype (g_{ij}) and on the allelic ADO rate (θ_L) under the LDO mode for DelSIEVE.

α_{ij}	g_{ij}	Number of alleles dropped out	$P(\alpha_{ij} g_{ij}, \theta_L)$
0	0/0	2	θ_L^2
1	0/0	1	$2\theta_L(1 - \theta_L)$
2	0/0	0	$(1 - \theta_L)^2$
0	0/1	2	θ_L^2
1	0/1	1	$2\theta_L(1 - \theta_L)$
2	0/1	0	$(1 - \theta_L)^2$
0	1/1	2	θ_L^2
1	1/1	1	$2\theta_L(1 - \theta_L)$
2	1/1	0	$(1 - \theta_L)^2$
0	1/1'	2	θ_L^2
1	1/1'	1	$2\theta_L(1 - \theta_L)$
2	1/1'	0	$(1 - \theta_L)^2$
0	0/-	1	θ_L
1	0/-	0	$1 - \theta_L$
0	1/-	1	θ_L
1	1/-	0	$1 - \theta_L$
0	-	0	1
		Others	0

Table S3: Evolutionary rate matrix used in the simulator to generate the simulated data for DelSIEVE. Genotypes are encoded with nucleotides rather than numbers. d is the deletion rate measured relatively to the mutation rate. The diagonal elements are denoted by dots, and have negative values equal to the sum of the other entries in the same row, ensuring that the sum of each row equals zero.

	A/A	A/C	A/G	A/T	C/C	C/G	C/T	G/G	G/T	T/T	-A	-C	-G	-T	-
A/A	.	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	d	0	0	0	0
A/C	$\frac{1}{6}$.	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	0	0	$\frac{d}{2}$	$\frac{d}{2}$	0	0	0
A/G	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$.	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	$\frac{d}{2}$	0	$\frac{d}{2}$	0	0
A/T	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$.	0	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{d}{2}$	0	0	$\frac{d}{2}$	0
C/C	0	$\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	.	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	0	0	d	0	0	0
C/G	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	$\frac{1}{6}$.	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	0	$\frac{d}{2}$	$\frac{d}{2}$	0	0
C/T	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$.	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	$\frac{d}{2}$	0	$\frac{d}{2}$	0
G/G	0	0	$\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	$\frac{1}{3}$	0	.	$\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	0	d	0	0
G/T	0	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$.	$\frac{1}{6}$	0	0	$\frac{d}{2}$	$\frac{d}{2}$	0
T/T	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{3}$	0	0	$\frac{1}{3}$	0	$\frac{1}{3}$.	0	0	0	d	0
-A	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	.	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{d}{2}$
-C	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{6}$.	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{d}{2}$
-G	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$.	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{d}{2}$
-T	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$	$\frac{1}{6}$.	$\frac{d}{2}$
-	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	.

Table S4: Summary of fractions of predicted genotypes by DelSIEVE and SIEVE for three analyzed real datasets. Entries marked with NA denote that the corresponding method does not call the specific genotype.

		-	1/-	0/-	0/0	0/1	1/1	1/1'
TNBC16	DelSIEVE	0	11.51%	0.07%	15.58%	69.82%	2.99%	0.03%
	SIEVE	NA	NA	NA	15.54%	75.11%	9.30%	0.05%
CRC28	DelSIEVE	0	0.15%	0.02%	25.02%	74.59%	0.16%	0.06%
	SIEVE	NA	NA	NA	25.02%	74.64%	0.28%	0.06%
CRC48	DelSIEVE	0	0	0.08%	59.61%	40.17%	0.14%	0
	SIEVE	NA	NA	NA	59.48%	40.50%	0.02%	0